

Trade Union Experiences and Perspectives on Artificial Intelligence and Workplace Transformation: Critical AI Literacy as a Tool for Empowerment

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STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of the contribution

This contribution reports on research in progress which aims to explore the implications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the workplace from the perspective of trade unions. It focuses on establishing how the critical understanding and deployment of AI can empower unions, and by extension workers, to respond to the challenges and opportunities that AI presents to the persistent decent work deficits (ILO, 2024), forming a foundation for the critical AI literacy framework.

Value of the contribution

The presentation offers valuable insights for researchers and practitioners interested in the intersections of information science, labour, and social justice. It contributes a novel perspective to information literacy (IL), by linking critical AI literacy with the agency of workers and unions. By exploring how unionists perceive and use AI—and how critical literacy can function as a tool of empowerment—the study informs future directions in AI/IL training, collective bargaining, and policy. Trade unions, as underexplored empirical sites, provide a lens through which to understand how collective knowledge practices evolve under technological disruption. The research foregrounds collective information strategies that resist deskilling, surveillance, and the erosion of rights, while promoting critical engagement with AI systems. Developing a critical AI literacy that situates AI within socio-technical and power structures is essential—not only for individuals, but for collectives advocating for decent work and democratic technology. This research may facilitate a well-informed multidisciplinary dialogue on AI which IL researchers are uniquely positioned to lead (Flierl, 2024), helping address a pressing

question for the field: 'how can we foster IL amid and beyond the AI revolution?' (Hirvonen, 2024: 50).

Research outline

- **Research context:** AI is becoming ubiquitous in the workplace, raising a widespread anxiety about its disruptive effects on workers' rights (Ponce, 2018) and decent work, such as job losses and a lack of autonomy (OECD, 2023). AI particularly affects workers' and unions' agentic power to curb its deleterious effects and ensure it delivers for all. To be able to contest its deployment and assert themselves in a rapidly changing work environment (Ponce, 2018), they need to develop an understanding of the role and the (in)visible impact of AI on work along with a capacity to engage critically with it, i.e. develop AI and critical workplace information literacy (Šobota, 2023).
- **Research aims:** The research aims to investigate the extent and the potential deployment of AI to advance workers' rights and to establish a framework for critical AI literacy instruction supportive of a decent work agenda. It seeks to explore the current and potential use of AI by unions; perceived benefits and risks; anticipated impacts on the world of work and union activity; the skills and training that unionists need for using AI to advance workers' rights and for evaluating critically its functioning and outputs; and the role of unions in respect of AI.
- **Design/methodology:** The survey method was employed, with a quantitative online questionnaire comprising 31 mostly closed questions. After establishing face validity and pilot-testing the questionnaire on a subset of the intended population, responses were gathered during January and February 2025 on an online survey platform Google Forms. Convenience sampling comprised 304 participants, Croatian trade unionists (union activists, union reps, occupational health and safety reps, works council members, union experts and leaders), with most respondents having over 16 years of union experience. The sample spanned more than 50 individual trade unions, with participants predominantly coming from professional or local/company-level unions, concentrated in education and science, health and social care, and the non-profit sector. Data were analysed with SPSS and Excel.
- **Findings:** Research revealed limited use of AI in union work, with most users engaging rarely and primarily for text writing, finding or sharing information and communicating with members, for translation purposes and for coordinating union activities and collective

actions. Respondents also used AI for personal learning and for data analysis, generating ideas, creating visual content, supporting union organising and collective bargaining, providing advice to members and delivering or improving union education. Reported benefits include time savings and improved information access, while the barriers pertain mostly to lack of knowledge and skills or absence of perceived need. While respondents anticipate moderate to significant—largely positive—effects on union work, they also express concern about AI's negative, dehumanising effects on work, alongside the increased need for new skills. Most self-rated their AI-related knowledge and skills as low, and expressed strong need for training, particularly in digital and AI literacy, critical thinking, and legal regulation. There was overwhelming support for union involvement in AI governance through worker education, inclusive implementation, policy advocacy, collective bargaining, and research.

- **Research limitations/implications:**

This study provides initial insights into union experiences with, and perspectives on, AI and into how unions and, by extension, workers' more generally, might learn to make best use of it to advance a more collectivist agenda—a topic underexplored in information science and IL research. While it captures a broad cross-section of views, its findings are shaped by geographic specificity, the early stage of AI adoption, and respondents' self-assessments and perceptions. Building on these indicative findings, further research will involve qualitative exploration, via focus groups and interviews, to build a more nuanced, practice-oriented framework for critical AI literacy in workplace context, to empower union actors in navigating AI's challenges and opportunities and shaping its ethical and equitable use in the workplace.

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